

MODULAR AVIONICS: ITS IMPACTS ON COMMUNICATION, NAVIGATION,
AND IDENTIFICATION (CNI)

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ABSTRACT

The impacts of modular integrated avionics on radio CNI is discussed from several viewpoints: 1) system design, 2) specifications, 3) cost, 4) market effects, and 5) supportability. It is concluded that system designs, market practices, and maintenance and support will appreciably change; resulting in enhanced mission effectiveness at optimum costs to the DOD.

INTRODUCTION

For several decades modular avionics has ameliorated problems of maintainability, supportability, and cost. With the advent of integrated avionics like integrated communication, navigation, and identification (CNI) systems, additional advantages of significant size, weight, and power reductions are being forecast as a result of the confluence of modular avionics, digital electronics, and integrated circuit technologies. Integrated CNI has its architecture and partitioning based on this confluence, and aims to provide solutions to the collective problems of logistics, maintenance, cost, and operational efficiency.

Among the reasons that exist for the accelerating trend of modular avionics are changing business strategies, budgetary constraints, and requirements to counter new threats. (1)

In October 1986, Congress advised the DOD to prepare a joint plan to include fully integrated, digital avionics on all aircraft under development. In response, the three Services developed a joint integrated avionics plan for new aircraft that called for future utilization of common, line-replaceable modules. With these modules, system designers would build standardized subsystems such as signal processors, data processors, integrated CNI, and integrated electronic warfare (EW). To implement this plan the Joint Integrated Avionics Working Group (JIAWG) was formed to produce specifications for modules, an avionics architecture, high-speed data bus, avionics computer, packaging, connectors, and backplane. The group will also issue specifications for reusable software modules. (2)

This paper will attempt to focus on some of the issues of modular avionics, common modules, and standard modules as they relate to the CNI community.

CHARACTERISTICS OF CNI

A look at CNI avionics of thirty years ago reveals their characteristic designs were discrete, stand-alone, packages for separate communications, navigation, or identification functions. These were packaged as "black boxes" for specific airplanes. Use of the term CNI as a noun began to be used more and more during the late 1950s and early 1960s as the possibility of integrating the functions occurred.

In 1958, the CNI radio market represented a major economic force in electronics, plus a major consumer of vacuum tubes. Vacuum tube technology could not support functional integration because of its ancillary system complexities. Solutions were to later lay with solid-state devices, digital electronics and software. At that time, there was a strong incentive to optimize individual communications, navigation, and identification avionics as entities. Emphasis in new systems focused on replacement by form, fit, and function of separate radios. Due to the power, size, and weight requirements of vacuum tube technology, there were definite limits on how much CNI capability a small airplane could carry...power dissipation and reliability being major considerations.

By 1969, the problem of proliferating boxes could no longer be ignored. A descriptive example was: "...the USAF C-141 aircraft employs approximately 76 electronic boxes with 27 associated antennas for CNI functions." (3)

The progression of CNI architectures from the era of vacuum tubes to future technologies is shown in Figure 1. Original implementations followed a strict separation of communication, navigation, and identification subsystems as Figure 1a depicts. Thus, each radio included sensors (RF low noise amplification circuitry), analog processing (demodulation and modulation), and controls and displays (radio controls, readouts, and audio). Today's evolving CNI avionics are represented in Figure 1b. Within these systems, functional CNI integration occurs via common modules and resource sharing. The Navy's Tactical Information Exchange System (TIES) (4), and the tri-service Integrated Communication, Navigation, Identification Avionics (ICNIA) program (5) are representative types.

The approach uses software to effect system control and waveform processing, yet CNI is identifiably separate from other avionics. CNI thus becomes analogous to an avionics subsystem. The future concept for CNI, illustrated in Figure 1c,

subsumes CNI into total aircraft integration,

FIGURE 1. THE EVOLUTION OF CNI ARCHITECTURES. (A) DISCRETE SYSTEMS OF YESTERDAY; (B) INTEGRATED CNI OF TODAY; (C) FUTURE CNI AS A PART OF INTEGRATED AVIONICS

Perhaps the only identifiable remnants being the sensors. The PAVE PILLAR concept is representative of this approach. (6) Such an architecture raises the level of avionics in importance to that of airframe, propulsion, and armaments in the development of future weapons. (7)

INTEGRATED CNI

A representative CNI architecture is shown in Figure 2. From an architecture-design viewpoint, individual functions of communication, navigation, and identification identities are being replaced by shared resources in the form of common modules divided among an RF (analog) group, a signal processing group, and a data processing group.

Design requirements for specific CNI functions are partitioned among modules using software with the following guidelines:

- a. Red/Black separation
- b. TEMPEST considerations
- c. Intra- and inter-face complexities
- d. Functional commonality within CNI modes
- e. Loopback test paths for built-in-test (BIT)
- f. Minimizing module types
- g. Expandability with minimum special modules
- h. Control partitioning by time criticality

Modularity permits systems to be configured for many applications and to be tailored for mission requirements; and configuration gives them an ability to be used for many different platforms. The common denominators are standard building-block modules and tailored software. The right mix of modules, interfaces, and application-specific software permits minimum CNI development costs for the tri-Service.

Integrated CNI circuitry is packaged in plug-in modules that are individually replaceable at the

Organization Level and are designed to be serviced by minimally-trained support personnel. With the use of BIT and platform/weapon system diagnostics, the goals are to achieve fault detection, isolation, and false alarm rates at the module level of 0.98, 0.95, and 0.01, respectively. The effects of these, hopefully, will be reduced personnel costs, plus higher CNI availability, which together translate into greater weapon system supportability and readiness.

MODULES

A representative CNI digital module is shown in Figure 3. This module's configuration was developed specifically to demonstrate that integrated CNI could be efficiently packaged in a flight worthy, modular manner for two-level maintenance. Its form factor is a 3/4 ATR size. The module consists of an EMI/RFI protected, environmentally-tolerant, "clam shell" that encloses two printed circuit board (PCB) assemblies. It is compatible with both ATR and Integrated Rack housing concepts. This design is only one of many representative ones that have been proposed as a standard for DOD consideration.

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FIGURE 2. AN INTEGRATED CNI SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE. THE SYSTEM IS MADE UP OF MODULES THAT CAN COLLECTIVELY HANDLE CNI SIGNALS BETWEEN 2 MHZ AND 2000 MHZ

FIGURE 3. A REPRESENTATIVE MODULE FOR INTEGRATED CNI SYSTEMS. THE MODULE HAS A 3/4 ATR FORM FACTOR AND IS COMPATIBLE WITH LINE REPLACEABLE UNITS AND/OR INTEGRATED RACK HOUSINGS. (TRW INC.)

The total number of unique module types depends upon specific CNI functions that are to be implemented. For three different CNI configurations that have been defined for tactical aircraft and helicopters, a total of approximately 28 different module types have been identified. Total module count in the most complex of the configurations is approximately 100. This total includes module redundancy to satisfy fault tolerance. A numerical comparison of the integrated CNI module types with discrete CNI modules required for the same functions is illustrated in Figure 4.

CNI FUNCTION	DISCRETE SYSTEM	INTEGRATED SYSTEM
HF TRANSCEIVER	7	ICNIA ADM
UHF TRANSCEIVER	7	
VHF TRANSCEIVER	7	
ILS/VOR	6	
TACAN	10	
IFF TRANSPONDER (I&T)	21	
JTIDS	60	
TOTAL MODULE TYPES	138	28

FIGURE 4. A NUMERICAL COMPARISON OF MODULE TYPES BETWEEN DISCRETE CNI SYSTEMS AND AN INTEGRATED CNI SYSTEM.

The effects of reducing the number of module types are an expected increase in reliability and a lessening of the logistics burden.

Modular avionics and common modules, as conceptualized by integrated CNI will stem the proliferation of military modules of similar functional elements.

EFFECTS OF SPECIFYING

If a module's functional, mechanical, and thermal parameters, plus interfaces can be defined, then current production and manufacturing techniques might advance with the state-of-the-art. This could have beneficial effects for retrofitted CNI as well as new systems.

A module's specifications will cover requirements for its form, fit, and function, rather than its detailed design requirements. The idea is to permit module vendors to produce modules without unnecessarily restricting components and specific design details as long as the functional requirements of the specification are maintained.

Acquisition of CNI systems based on modules is expected to be more economical to the DOD because: (a) vendors can use those design and components that are compatible with their established facilities and techniques, (b) vendors can pursue cost savings through technological advances and personal innovations, and (c) the market of competitors can be made large. The expected results of these are reduced engineering development costs, reduced development time, and more realistic cost bids for system developments. Many of these expectations have been realized in the Navy's Standard Electronics Module (SEM) program. (8)

Government experience with the SEM program has shown that on the average, SEMs are characterized by a failure rate one-fifth as large as that of unique or custom modules. (8),(9)

In 1974, the Government developed representative costs for introducing new modules into their SEM program. Table 1 shows this result. (9)

Vendor's Costs		
Design:	\$7.8K	30%
Spec. & Data Prep.:	8.8K	34%
Build Docum'tation:	2.2K	8%
Build, Design, & Qual.:	2.8K	11%
Production Start:	4.4K	17%
Totals:	26.0K	100%
Government's Costs		
Correlate Data:	3.3K	21%
Correlate Vendor:	1.1K	7%
1st Qualification:	5.6K	36%
Design Evaluation:	5.6K	36%
Totals:	15.6K	100%

Table 1. Cost breakouts for entering a Simple Digital Module into the Standard Digital Module (SDM) Inventory. Three other classes of modules were identified (1) Complex = 1.1 x SDM; (2) Very Complex = 1.8 x SDM; and (3) Extremely Complex = 3.6 x SDM. See reference 9.

Significant savings were realized due to: reduced costs associated with introducing and sustaining a new module in the Federal Supply System, reduced spare parts required throughout DOD; competitively-procured parts through the life cycle of the system, and reduced obsolescence of parts due to the slower decay of modules compared to individual integrated circuits or components in general.

During the production phases of programs, it was found that SEMs had advantages of reduced costs for test equipment, lower prices due to multiple competitive sources, and savings due to economy of scale (learning curve) factors. (10)

COST CONSIDERATIONS

Economics makes the compelling argument for modular CNI. Analytical models are used to aid decisions about their development. These models typically use life-cycle cost as the "bottom-line" determinant for proceeding with a new design. Emphasis is placed on the differences between system costs of an integrated modular system and a collection of discrete systems that perform the same functions. MIL-HDBK-246A presents a costing methodology for evaluating the two options. (11).

According to the handbook, total costs are partitioned into the following phases of a system's development:

- a. Research and Development
- b. Acquisition/Production
- c. Operation and Support
- d. Retirement and disposal

As presented, this model only covers module costs. The interconnecting backplane, support structure, card cages, software, integration costs, and retrofit costs are not covered. These costs constitute a considerable omission and must be added to the analysis.

Cost models are typically classified according to three types: (a) accounting types, (b) parametric types, and (c) cost-estimating relationships (CERs). Modular CNI systems have generally used portions of all three types because of the many unknowns associated with new technology and the early stage of development of such systems.

The approach taken for integrated CNI has been to compare their development costs, acquisition costs, and maintenance costs with collective discrete systems over their expected lives.

Problems confronting the cost analyst of integrated CNI include the uncertainties associated with: new technologies, new architectures and interfaces, and new software algorithms.

THE CNI MARKET

The CNI business community historically evolved from companies that specialized in only one or possibly a few, discrete C, N, or I functions. These may have included HF, UHF, VHF; or special radios such as ILS, TACAN, weather radar, etc.

Modular avionics' impact on CNI will likely be a forced redefinition of business and organizational strategies for supplying these functions. Its effect on business strategy arises from the fact that discrete functions will lose their individual identities as time passes into the next century. Technology's explosion in the digital domain implies "system engineering" as the main discipline for future avionics development. CNI and other specialists will likely be required to submerge their individual interests under the broader need for platform-integrated architectures. Important specialties that can be foreseen are those of "systems engineer", "interface designer", or "digital interface engineer", whose work will be that of defining and developing interfaces for the new system architectures.

From a business viewpoint, a relook at products and product lines is in order. With the gradual disappearance of discrete radio functions in the world of integrated avionics, the focus will be on those "nodes" and "interfaces" of predefined architectures. Thus, the issue is: what replaces the UHF radio? One possibility is that this radio will evolve into a "sensor"...sharing some modular hardware, software, and functionally with other electronics in a hierarchical architecture. The sensor will, therefore, include products that overlap those of the higher-level system: A/D converters, signal processors, data processors, I/O management, and data buses. Figure 5 attempts to illustrate this "environment" of the future.

The interdependence of each area in Figure 5 is forced by concepts of resource-sharing, fault tolerance, and common modules. Equally important to the design of hardware will be design of CNI control software. As hardware provides the "muscle," software provides the "brains" for integrated systems. Economical algorithms and software for control, self-test, and fault tolerance are presently the most important unsolved problems related

FIGURE 5. THE MODULAR INTEGRATED CNI ENVIRONMENT

to integrated CNI. A "systems" approach, crossing hardware and software boundaries, plus crossing traditional C, N, and I organizations is expected to solve these problems.

Much of industry reflects its government customers in terms of its organization. As these customers change, industry will probably change. Thus, as reorganizations occur in governmental agencies a "ripple effect" can be expected. Government reorganizations will probably result from logistics and supportability changes caused by modular avionics. This might especially occur if two-level maintenance for avionics becomes a universal reality.

Another probable impact on the CNI market will be constraints on CNI architecture designs caused by module resource-sharing and pre-definitions of module size, form factor, I/O, and airplane integration strategies.

Unique problems for the Government will be certification of modules and management of warranties at the systems level. Fortunately, experience under its SEM program might provide direction in these areas.

SUPPORTABILITY AND LOGISTICS ISSUES

An important aspect of maintainability and logistics support is module interchangeability... that is, the capability of a module from one manufacturer to be removed and a like module installed in its place, provided by another manufacturer. With variations that often occur in different production processes, it may be possible to accomplish maintainability demonstrations on sample numbers of integrated CNI modules from several manufacturers' production lots, to ensure that quality control is maintained.

Integrated CNI systems are being designed with two levels of maintenance in mind: the flightline and depot.

Support issues include: test and support of CNI systems, module support, test and support equipment, personnel and training, technical data, facilities, transportation and handling, and maintenance planning. CNI test and support equipment include all tools, monitoring and checkout equipment, calibration, maintenance test stands, and handling equipment required to support scheduled and unscheduled maintenance actions

associated with CNI. Many of these problems have the potential to be solved with the help of knowledge gleaned from the Integrated Electromagnetic System Simulator (IESS) program (12) plus BIT that is part of the integrated system itself.

IESS is being developed as a baseline test and evaluation hot bench facility for CNI maintenance. Among its design objectives are the following: (a) to provide a real-time simulated EW environment for CNI, and (b) to provide a software support environment for future CNI systems. Figure 6 illustrates the relationship between the IESS and an integrated CNI system. As a prototype depot test facility, IESS provides a potential for using many of the same modules that the integrated CNI system itself uses, thereby achieving further cost and logistic advantages.

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FIGURE 6. THE INTEGRATED ELECTROMAGNETIC SYSTEM SIMULATOR (IESS) IS BEING DEVELOPED TO ACQUIRE KNOWLEDGE FOR THE SUPPORT OF INTEGRATED AVIONICS SYSTEMS.

Modular CNI provides an opportunity for extensive interservice sharing of common module research and development costs, plus engineering costs. These "investment costs" can thus be lower than when each Service independently creates its unique systems.

Efforts to control costs and logistics support for an ever-growing avionics inventory have resulted in tri-Service attempts to define common modules that can be used across-functions, weapon systems, and support equipments. Many of the same arguments against standardization (i.e., non-optimization of performance, size and weight penalty, and innovation and technology impedance) can apply to standard modules. CNI designers, developers, and producers will, therefore, have to deal with more predetermined variables no longer under their control.

A major constraint that slows usage of new technology internationally is that worldwide standards are required in order that radio transmitters and receivers will work together. Changes are further delayed to allow time for new equipment to be manufactured, and still more to allow amortization of old equipment. General usage lags technology by 10 to 20 years when major changes in international standards, such as those agreed upon by NATO, are involved. The use of common modules in integrated systems could speed up the application of new capabilities and new technologies for

multi-national use.

CONCLUSIONS

The effects of modular avionics on CNI can be summarized as follows: first, modular architectures will change future military and industry business practices. It is envisioned that major discrete functions currently found in avionics such as communications, navigation, and identification will disappear...replaced by highly integrated CNI sensors whose hardware and software will be built largely from common, multi-use modules. The implication is that future-equipment product changes will be forced within DOD and on company product lines.

Second, CNI functional differences will consist primarily of software algorithms, and customized sensor-effector modules. This will lead to new engineering specialties, and software management techniques in both Government and industry.

Third, standard, multi-use CNI common modules will be procured competitively from many sources by a single DOD agency for tri-Service, multi-purpose applications. This should result in lower prices to DOD and result in new industries, organizational charters, and government procurement policies.

Finally, it is envisioned that some traditional support functions such as the avionics intermediate shop, will drastically change. The resources devoted to its personnel training, deployment, and equipment could be redirected. CNI depot training and support, in contrast, is expected to grow in sophistication and capability.

Hopefully, these impacts will result in enhanced mission effectiveness at optimum cost for CNI avionics of the future.

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